

Research Article

Effect of Tillage System and Nitrogen Level on Growth of Maize (*Zea Mays* L.) in Northern Guinea Zone of Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

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A three year field study was conducted on the same field in 2006, 2007 and 2008 rainy seasons at the experimental farm of Institute for Agricultural Research (I.A.R.), Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria- Nigeria (Lat. 11° 11' N: Long 7° 38' E: 686 m above sea level) to determined the effect of tillage system and nitrogen level on the growth of Oba 98 maize variety. The treatment laid out in split plot design consisted of six tillage practices (harrowing followed by weeding, harrowing followed by primextra Gold, paraquat followed by primextra Gold, glyphosate followed by primextra Gold, ridging followed by weeding and ridging followed by primextra Gold followed by weeding) as the main plots while nitrogen level (0, 50, 100 and 150kgNha⁻¹) were assigned to sub plots. The results showed significant response of growth parameters and cob weight to some tillage systems. Glyphosate followed by primextra Gold significantly increased plant height, leaf area index, crop growth rate, relative growth rate and days to 50% tasseling. Paraquat followed by primextra Gold significantly increased plant height, harrowing followed by weeding significantly increased leaf area index, cob weight were significantly affected by paraquat followed by primextra Gold and glyphosate followed by primextra Gold. Nitrogen application significantly increased growth components such as plant height up to 100kgNha⁻¹, leaf area index up 50kgNha⁻¹, crop growth rate up to 100 kgNha⁻¹, relative growth rate up to 50kgNha⁻¹, number of days to 50% tasseling up to 150kgNha⁻¹ and cob weight 100 kgNha⁻¹

INTRODUCTION

Maize is one of the major important staple crops in west and central Africa. These sub regions have the greatest potential such as adequate moisture, abundant sunshine and relatively fertile soils for maize production (Badu Apraku *et al.*, 2006). The area planted to maize in west and central Africa increased from 3.2 million hectares in 1961 to 8.9 million hectares in 2005. The expansion of farm area devoted to maize resulted in increased production from 2.4 million metric tones in 1961 to 10.6 million metric tones in 2005 (FAO, 2006). As at 2010, the world maize production was 829 million tones with 8.1 million tones for Nigeria which is just 1.0% of the total world production (FAO, 2010). Tillage systems are sequences of operations that manipulate soil in order to prepare good seed bed for better crop production. The ways in which these operations are implemented affect physical and chemical properties of soil which in turn affect plant growth (Scott, 2008). Application of recommended dose of nitrogenous fertilizer to maize crop has an overriding effect on growth and has been reported to dominates the effects of other essential elements (Idem, 1989).

One of the most critical natural resources base on which Africa's food security depend is the soil of the continent. African soils are relatively more sensitive and fragile than those found in other continents and have over the years been considerably and consistently eroded by natural and man made factors. The causes of soil degradation in Africa are many and varied. These include over use and misuse of the soil, deforestation and other agricultural activities such as intensive tilling of soil. The impact of these factors manifested itself in stagnating and declining crop yield.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted during 2006, 2007 and 2008 wet seasons at the experimental farm of Institute for

Agricultural Research (I.A.R.), Ahmadu Bello University Zaria (Lat. 11° 11' N: Long. 7° 38' E: 686 m above sea level). The site is located in the Northern Guinea Savanna zone whose soil is predominantly sandy loam. The response of Oba 98 maize variety in term of growth to six tillage systems (harrowing followed by weeding, harrowing followed by primextra Gold, ridging followed by primextra Gold followed by weeding, ridging followed weeding, glyphosate followed by primextra Gold and paraquat followed by primextra Gold) and four levels of nitrogen (0, 50, 100 and 150kgNha⁻¹) were considered. A split plot design was used with tillage systems as the main plot while nitrogen levels were assigned to sub plot. The treatment were replicated five times. The gross plot consisted of four rows/ridges (0.75 m apart) by 3 m long of which the total area was 3m x 3m = 9.0m². The two centre rows (in no tilled) and two centre ridges (in tilled) formed the net plot while the two border rows/ridges formed the discard for measuring growth characters. Nitrogen in the form of urea (46%N) was applied at the rate of 0, 50, 100 and 150kgNha⁻¹. The application was done in two split doses. The first dose was applied at ten days after sowing along with P and K in form of single super phosphate and muriate of potash at the rate of 60kg P₂O₅ (26.18kg P) per hectare and 60kg K₂O (49.81kg K) per hectare respectively. The second dose was applied at five weeks after sowing. The fertilizer was incorporated in 5cm depth holes midway between stands. The data collected were plant height, leaf area index, crop growth rate, relative growth rate and days to 50% tasseling. General Linear Model procedure (GLM) of the Statistical Analysis System (SAS) package (SAS, 1990) was used in the statistical analysis of the data collected and differences between the treatment means were compared using Duncan Multiple Range Test as described by Duncan (1955). Table 1 shows the information on physical and chemical properties of the soil at the experimental field. Table 2, 3 and 4 shows the meteorological conditions of the area under study during the experimental periods.

Table 1, Physical and chemical properties of the experimental site soil for 2006, 2007 and 2008

TS	Base cations and CEC(cmolc/kg ⁻¹)														
	<u>2</u>	<u>0</u>	<u>0</u>	<u>6</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>0</u>	<u>0</u>	<u>7</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>0</u>	<u>0</u>	<u>8</u>	<u>0</u>	<u>0</u>	<u>8</u>
	Ca	Mg	K	Na	CEC	Ca	Mg	K	Na	CEC	Ca	Mg	K	Na	CEC
HW	1.67	0.97	0.25	0.26	5.20	1.56	0.88	0.34	0.28	5.21	1.77	0.97	0.4	0.26	4.53
HP	2.00	0.93	0.33	0.26	4.60	2.00	0.93	0.34	0.26	4.60	<u>2.80</u>	0.84	<u>0.42</u>	0.37	4.64
RW	1.99	1.28	0.27	0.23	4.90	1.97	1.28	0.27	0.21	4.90	1.99	1.28	0.27	0.21	4.93
PPx	<u>2.00</u>	<u>1.42</u>	<u>0.30</u>	<u>0.23</u>	5.20	<u>2.22</u>	<u>1.41</u>	<u>0.30</u>	<u>0.26</u>	5.20	<u>3.14</u>	<u>1.99</u>	<u>0.45</u>	<u>0.37</u>	5.89
RPW	1.99	1.03	0.12	0.26	4.30	1.94	1.03	0.12	0.26	3.80	1.99	1.00	0.12	0.20	4.33
GPx	<u>2.00</u>	1.52	<u>0.35</u>	<u>0.35</u>	4.20	<u>2.11</u>	2.10	<u>0.38</u>	<u>0.32</u>	4.10	<u>2.94</u>	2.10	<u>0.47</u>	<u>0.38</u>	5.10
TC	Sandy loam					Sandy loam					Sandy loam				

HW= harrowing followed by weeding, HPx= harrowing followed by primextra Gold, RW= ridging followed by weeding, PPx= paraquat followed by primextra Gold, RPxW=ridging followed by primextra Gold followed by weeding, GPx= glyphosate followed by primextra Gold, CEC= cat ion exchange capacity, TS= tillage system, TC=textural class

Table 2: Mean monthly temperatures, relative humidity, sunshine hours and rainfall at ten-day intervals during the period of the experiment in the wet season of the year 2006 at Samaru, Zaria-Nigeria

Month	Days	Max. temp. (°C)	Min. temp. (°C)	Relative humidity(%) am	Relative humidity(%) pm	Rainfall (mm)
May	0-10	35.6	22.9	63.0	41.5	47.0
	11-20	33.2	21.3	73.2	51.3	30.5
	21-31	35.5	22.9	77.9	60.5	-
June	0-10	32.7	22.3	67.7	51.3	4.4
	11-20	31.9	22.8	77.5	59.5	34.7
	21-30	35.3	21.0	71.6	57.5	87.4
July	0-10	30.8	21.4	77.0	67.8	14.2
	11-20	30.6	22.2	30.6	65.4	171.8
	21-31	34.0	22.6	79.3	73.1	42.6
August	0-10	29.5	20.8	82.4	68.3	74.8
	11-20	30.9	20.2	80.6	62.9	43.5
	21-31	32.4	22.4	91.3	83.6	103.7
September	0-10	30.2	19.7	82.5	74.1	70.8

	11-20	30.9	20.5	79.6	72.1	126.1
	21-30	31.6	20.2	78.5	63.9	78.7
October	0-10	32.1	20.5	74.7	69.5	21.8
	11-20	33.3	23.6	79.0	60.6	6.7
	21-31	34.7	21.7	59.7	42.1	-

Source: I.A.R. Meteorological Station, Samaru Zaria-Nigeria .

Table 3: Mean monthly temperatures, relative humidity, sunshine hours and rainfall at ten-day intervals during the period of the experiment in the wet season of the year 2007 at Samaru, Zaria-Nigeria

Month	Days	Max. temp. (°C)	Min. temp. (°C)	Relative humidity(% am	Relative humidity(% pm	Rainfall (mm)
May	0-10	34.1	21.3	65.5	34.0	96.0
	11-20	33.7	23.0	68.4	33.7	4.2
	21-31	37.6	23.2	77.0	37.6	69.2
June	0-10	31.5	20.4	74.4	31.7	71.0
	11-20	34.4	20.4	83.5	31.1	39.4
	21-30	30.8	20.3	79.0	30.8	60.3
July	0-10	30.8	21.4	82.0	30.8	25.0
	11-20	29.5	20.3	80.4	29.5	32.4
	21-31	29.2	20.6	76.3	29.2	168.8
August	0-10	28.8	20.8	71.4	28.8	51.1
	11-20	29.0	21.9	78.6	29.0	177.0
	21-31	31.5	23.2	88.8	31.5	146.2
September	0-10	28.7	20.7	84.1	29.1	16.4
	11-20	32.1	20.1	72.9	32.1	3.5
	21-30	33.3	19.9	67.0	37.5	1.2
October	0-10	34.0	19.0	64.9	34.0	4.9
	11-20	35.1	16.6	54.4	35.1	3.4
	21-31	39.2	20.7	63.7	39.2	-

Source: I. A. R. Meteorological Station, Samaru Zaria – Nigeria.

Table 4: Mean monthly temperatures, relative humidity, sunshine hours and rainfall at ten-day intervals during the period of the experiment in the wet season of the year 2008 at Samaru, Zaria-Nigeia

Month	Days	Max. temp. (°C)	Min. temp. (°C)	Relative humidity(%) am	Relative humidity(%) pm	Rainfall (mm)
May	0-10	37.7	23.0	49.0	34.1	23.8
	11-20	34.3	21.5	67.0	54.4	18.5
	21-31	36.4	23.3	79.1	63.2	52.9
June	0-10	33.4	20.6	71.9	54.7	68.1
	11-20	33.6	23.6	69.9	50.5	27.9
	21-30	32.3	20.6	75.2	60.1	15.7
July	0-10	30.5	19.9	78.7	71.6	58.4
	11-20	30.5	20.5	77.2	70.9	18.2
	21-31	33.6	21.7	90.8	68.1	124.7
August	0-10	29.9	19.4	81.6	76.4	165.7
	11-20	29.2	19.8	89.6	70.9	81.1
	21-31	33.0	21.1	90.9	79.7	105.8
September	0-10	30.8	25.1	78.5	67.7	115.5
	11-20	31.7	25.5	76.2	62.8	42.1
	21-30	31.7	25.8	76.5	67.5	45.8
October	0-10	32.1	20.3	76.1	68.5	67.2
	11-20	33.3	19.5	67.5	58.8	21.8
	21-31	37.6	16.7	38.6	33.3	-

Source: I.A.R. Meteorological Station Samaru, Zaria – Nigeria.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 5 shows the effect of tillage system and nitrogen level on plant height. In 2006, paraquat followed by primextra Gold produced significantly taller plants than ridging followed by weeding. In 2007, paraquat followed by primextra Gold, glyphosate followed by primextra Gold and ridging followed by primextra Gold followed by weeding produced significantly taller plants than the other tillage systems. In 2008, glyphosate followed by primextra Gold produced significantly tallest plants while harrowing followed by weeding produced the shortest plants. In 2006 and 2007, plant height increased significantly with nitrogen application up to 100kgNha⁻¹

while in 2008 plant height increased significantly with nitrogen application up to 150kgNha⁻¹.

The effect of tillage system and nitrogen on leaf area index is presented in Table 5. In 2006, harrowing followed by weeding and harrowing followed by primextra Gold produced significantly higher leaf area index than the other tillage systems except ridging followed by weeding which is significantly at par with all the treatments. In 2007, glyphosate followed by primextra Gold and harrowing followed by primextra Gold produced significantly higher leaf area index than harrowing followed by weeding while in 2008, harrowing followed by weeding produced significantly higher leaf area index than ridging followed by primextra Gold

followed by weeding. In 2006 and 2007, 150kgNha⁻¹ produced significantly highest leaf area index while 0kgNha⁻¹ had the least. In 2008, leaf area index increased significantly with nitrogen application up to 50kgNha⁻¹

. Table 6 shows the effect of tillage system and nitrogen on crop growth rate. In 2006, tillage system had no significant effect on crop growth rate. In 2007, harrowing followed by primextra Gold and ridging followed by primextra Gold followed by weeding produced significantly higher crop growth rate than harrowing followed by weeding and ridging followed by weeding. In 2008, glyphosate followed by primextra Gold produced significantly highest crop growth rate. In 2006 and 2008, crop growth rate increased significantly with nitrogen application up to 100kgNha⁻¹ while in 2007, 150kgNha⁻¹ produced significantly the highest crop growth rate whereas 0kgNha⁻¹ had the least.

Table 6 shows the effect of tillage system and nitrogen on relative growth rate. In 2006, tillage system had no significant effect on relative growth rate. In 2007, harrowing followed by primextra Gold and ridging followed by primextra Gold followed by weeding produced significantly higher relative growth rate than harrowing followed by weeding. In 2008, paraquat followed by primextra Gold and glyphosate followed by primextra Gold produced significantly the highest relative growth rate while harrowing followed by weeding had the least. In 2006, 2007 and 2008, relative growth rate increased significantly with nitrogen application up to 50kgNha⁻¹.

The effect of tillage system and nitrogen on number of days to 50% tasseling is presented in Table 7. In 2006 and 2007, ridging followed by primextra Gold followed by weeding had significantly the highest number of days to 50% tasseling than the other treatments while in 2008, paraquat followed by primextra Gold and ridging followed by primextra Gold followed by weeding had significantly the longest period to 50% tasseling than the other treatments. In 2006 and 2007 tasseling was significantly delayed with nitrogen application up to 100kgNha⁻¹ while in 2008, tasseling was significantly delayed with nitrogen application up to 150 kgNha⁻¹. The effect of tillage system and nitrogen on cob weight is presented in Table 7. In 2006, paraquat followed by primextra Gold produced significantly higher cob weight than ridging followed by weeding. In 2007, paraquat followed by primextra Gold produced significantly the highest cob weight while in 2008, paraquat followed by primextra Gold and glyphosate followed by primextra Gold produced significantly the highest cob weight. In 2006 and 2008, cob weight significantly increased with nitrogen application up to 100 kgNha⁻¹ while in 2007 it was up to 150 kgNha⁻¹.

When growth pattern and cob weight were observed across the three years of study, it was recorded that the better growth in 2006 and 2008 could be attributed to the optimum intensity and uniform distribution of rainfall within the growing periods. The rainfall in these years extended to the second decade of October (Table 2 and 4). The poor growth recorded in 2007 could be due to the erratic pour down coupled with premature cessation of the rainfall which retreated in the first week of September (Table 3). Optimum temperatures (29.9°C- 34.0°C, 28.7°C-34.0°C and 29.2°C-33.6°C in 2006, 2007 and 2008 respectively) for plant growth were attained in all the three year of study. In 2008, the glyphosate followed by primextra Gold and paraquat followed by primextra Gold tillage practices enhanced plant height, leaf area index, crop growth rate, relative growth rate and days to 50% tasseling and cob weight compared with the other years. As the soil of the above two tillage systems were not tilled for three years, crop residue therefore remained on the soil surface where layer of mulch was produced. The layer protected the soil from physical impact of rain drops, wind and also improved soil structure for optimum moisture retention and possibly soil temperature regulation for better roots growth. The no-till provides and maintains favorable root zone environment as a result of moisture retention and temperature regulation that enable roots to function effectively without restriction in capturing high amount of plant nutrients and water for better plant growth (Derpsch, 2005).

The growth characters under consideration were found to be significantly affected by nitrogen application throughout the periods of study. As one of the major ingredients for chlorophyll formation, nitrogen played significant role in the photosynthesis processes during which a lot of assimilate was formed and translocated to different parts of the maize plant for tissue formation, growth through cell division and elongation as well as cob formation from the surplus assimilate. Nitrogen application could therefore be responsible for the significant increase in plant growth and cob weight as well. This finding is in line with that of Idem (1989) who reported that nitrogen application significantly increased all morphological parts (stem, leaf, inflorescence and roots) of maize plant. Similar observation was made by Ibrahim et al., (2008) that nitrogen application significantly increased plant height by increasing the length and number of internodes.

Based on this study, the best growth and heavier cob formation of Oba 98 maize variety was observed under glyphosate followed by primextra Gold and paraquat followed by primextra Gold tillage systems along with nitrogen application (up to 150kgNha⁻¹) under rain fed conditions.

Table 5: Effect of tillage system and nitrogen level on plant height and leaf area index of Oba 98 maize variety in 2006, 2007, and 2008 wet seasons at Samaru.

Treatment	Plant height (cm)			Leaf area index		
	2006	2007	2008	2006	2007	2008
Tillage system						
HfbW	123.99ab	126.93b	144.10c	2.13a	2.21b	3.28a
PfbPx	128.26a	140.17a	151.60b	1.87b	2.58ab	2.79ab
GfbPx	125.42ab	141.17a	167.81a	1.85b	2.91a	2.98ab
HfbPx	127.31ab	131.43b	149.85b	2.22a	3.24a	3.06ab
RfbPxfbW	125.77ab	147.75a	154.75b	1.73b	2.53ab	2.63b
RfbW	118.95b	127.10b	152.85b	2.00ab	2.29ab	3.09ab
SE±	2.676	2.618	2.266	0.211	0.202	0.169
Nitrogen(kg ha⁻¹)						
0	80.05c	117.68c	130.41d	1.20c	2.17c	2.24b
50	99.07b	130.46b	180.37c	1.96b	2.81b	3.07a
100	113.84a	144.75a	163.91b	2.22ab	3.10ab	3.30a
150	137.63a	149.93a	169.25a	2.50a	3.12a	3.28a
SE±	2.185	2.140	1.850	0.014	0.116	0.119
Interaction						
CT x N	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS

Means followed by different letter(s) are significantly different at 5% level of probability NS = Not significant GfbP_x = Glyphosate followed by Primextra Gold, HfbP_x = Harrow followed by Primextra Gold, HfbW = Harrowing followed by Weeding. PfbP_x = Paraquat followed by Primextra Gold, RfbPxfbW= Ridging followed by Primextra Gold followed by Weeding, RfbW = Ridging followed by Weeding, fb = followed by

Table 6: Effect of tillage system and nitrogen level on crop growth rate and relative growth rate of Oba 98 maize variety in 2006, 2007, and 2008 wet seasons at Samaru.

Treatment	Crop growth rate (ggm ²)			Relative growth rate(ggwk ⁻¹)		
	2006	2007	2008	2006	2007	2008
Tillage system						
HfbW	252.54	109.10b	120.08d	6.51	5.23c	5.44c
PfbPx	242.62	136.67ab	134.14cd	6.42	5.48abc	6.49a
GfbPx	275.55	134.98ab	188.91a	6.49	5.59ab	6.80a
HfbPx	227.02	160.64a	143.08bcd	6.14	5.81a	5.63b
RfbPxfbW	259.94	153.59a	155.23bc	6.48	5.81a	5.77b
RfbW	219.79	118.83b	161.37b	6.24	5.36bc	5.84b
SE±	2.341	1.234	1.976	0.160	0.110	0.150
Nitrogen(kg ha⁻¹)						
0	143.21c	94.52c	92.62c	5.61b	5.06b	5.05b
50	235.41b	134.67b	147.41b	6.41a	5.62a	5.73a
100	302.10a	146.81ab	175.72a	6.76a	5.66a	5.99a
150	304.25	166.53a	185.04a	6.75a	5.85a	5.88a
SE±	1.911	1.007	1.797	0.130	0.100	0.120
Interaction						
CT x N	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS

Means followed by different letter(s) are significantly different at 5% level of probability NS = Not significant GfbP_x = Glyphosate followed by Primextra Gold, HfbP_x = Harrow followed by Primextra Gold, HfbW = Harrowing followed by Weeding. PfbP_x = Paraquat followed by Primextra Gold, RfbPxfbW= Ridging followed by Primextra Gold followed by Weeding, RfbW = Ridging followed by Weeding, fb = followed by

Table 7: Effect of tillage system and nitrogen level on number of days to 50% tasselling and cob weight per hectare of Oba 98 maize variety in 2006, 2007 and 2008 wet seasons at Samaru.

Treatment	2006	2007	2008	Cob weight (kg ha ⁻¹)		
				2006	2007	2008
Tillage system						
HfbW	56.0b	51.0d	50.0d	1776.60ab	1450.20ab	1593.10c
PfbPx	56.0b	54.0b	58.0a	2233.80a	1691.50a	2955.40a
GfbPx	55.0b	53.0b	56.0b	1971.60ab	1425.60ab	3085.20a
HfbPx	50.0c	52.0c	56.0b	2056.60ab	1283.20b	1987.10b
RfbPxfbW	57.0a	56.0a	57.0a	2071.80ab	1486.60ab	2058.60b
RfbW	56.0b	51.0d	52.0c	1693.60b	960.20c	1562.30c
SE±	0.28	0.30	0.08	169.070	100.120	97.075
Nitrogen(kg ha⁻¹)						
0	46.0c	46.0c	47.0d	734.30c	557.50d	713.70c
50	49.0b	51.0b	51.0c	1732.40b	1078.00c	2630.90b
100	63.0a	57.0a	58.0b	2600.40a	1689.80b	4592.20a
150	63.0a	57.0a	60.0a	2602.30a	2006.30a	4557.70a
SE±	0.23	0.27	0.17	138.052	89.750	121.443
Interaction						
CT x N	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS

Means followed by different letter(s) are significantly different at 5% level of probability NS = Not significant GfbPx = Glyphosate followed by Primextra Gold, HfbPx = Harrow followed by Primextra Gold, HfbW = Harrowing followed by Weeding. PfbPx = Paraquat followed by Primextra Gold, RfbPxfbW= Ridging followed by Primextra Gold followed by Weeding, RfbW = Ridging followed by Weeding, fb = followed by

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